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Abstract: In order to carry out research at the points of intersection of architecture and construction with language, it is necessary to clarify several concepts and paradigms related to this process. Regarding the definition of the term, there are a lot of opinions expressed in scientific sources. In almost all definitions, the term is described as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept. In this article has shown the influence of word and term in national lexicon.

Key words: function, tagged, linguistic concepts, morphological-syntactic signs, semantic, syntactic information

Globalization and civilization processes, which continue continuously and productively throughout the world, have also brought great changes to the field of construction and architecture. The emergence of new types of raw materials, changes in construction forms and methods, adaptation to social needs and the demands of the times, and the improvement of the techniques and technologies used in this process, in parallel, lead to the assimilation of new field terms from other languages or the creation of them using internal capabilities, and to the active use of communicants in everyday life and which in turn affects the social lexicon.

In order to carry out research at the points of intersection of architecture and construction with language, it is necessary to clarify several concepts and paradigms related to this process. Regarding the definition of the term, there are a lot of opinions expressed in scientific sources. In almost all definitions, the term is described as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept. For example, the linguist V. P. Danilenko admits that the perception of any process occurring in society is first expressed in terminology or occurs as a result of transformational changes of certain terms.

Despite the wide range of researches carried out in the field of terminology, researches related to the terminology of some fields have not yet been completed. But it should also be noted that whatever language it is, its lexicon and the terminology included in this lexical scope are constantly being updated in line with the times. This naturally gives rise to the idea that the lexicon of the language needs constant research and research.

At this point, let's dwell on the factors that influenced the formation of Uzbek and English terms of construction architecture. Uzbek architecture, which is considered one of the central centers of civilization of Eastern architecture and architectural art, has its own ancient and rich historical development and traditions. The richness and attractiveness of Uzbek construction-architecture, which was able to create its own building principles and style according to its geographical, cultural and national characteristics, was formed on the basis of the trends characteristic of the Turkic peoples, and combines painting, carving, decoration and several other national cultural directions, is also reflected in the terminology of the field. .

The social, political and historical factors that occurred in this area determined certain criteria for the architecture of each period. During the 13th-18th centuries, tims, rabots, mosque-

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madrasas, palaces for rulers, defensive fortresses, mausoleums, etc. played an important role in the formation of the city's architectural appearance, and the names of the equipment, forms, and methods related to the field were partly influenced by the Arabic and Persian-Tajik languages in a certain sense. (Uzbek) language played a big role. As a result of subsequent political processes, the image of Russian architecture began to enter the country. In the 19th and 20th centuries, the construction of high-rise buildings, public buildings, etc., typical of Russian architecture, flourished not only in the city centers, but also in the districts and rural villages. As a result, the Uzbek architecture-construction field terminology has been enriched through the acquisition of Russian-international terms. Among the borrowed terms, there is an active encounter of terms borrowed from other languages through the Russian language. In particular, we can cite the following examples of terms introduced through the Russian language.

Parts of the building: roof, basement, attic, warehouse, hallway, floor..;

Names of equipment:zip, concrete mixer..;

Product names: brick, stone..;

The Soviet power, which kept our region and people under its influence for more than a century, was able to leave indelible traces in the field of construction and architecture. Due to the fact that the builders or employers who carried out architectural and construction works in our country for more than half a century were mainly representatives of the Russian language, many Russian construction and architectural terms have become "relics" for the Uzbek language. This can be explained by the importation and active use of construction equipment and materials from Russia and neighboring regions, the fact that the master builders spoke Russian and the language of construction and architecture was also Russian, as well as the high tendency to teach and learn the Russian language in the social life of that time. Today, Uzbek equivalents and alternatives of Russian architecture-construction terms, like other field terms, are offered for language users. For example: chot - hole, kraska - paint, brick - brick. But their adoption by the living language is very slow. The development and use of a dictionary of construction-architecture terms in the Uzbek language would have greatly accelerated this process.

But another aspect of the matter is that it is much more difficult from the point of view of the present day that the terms of construction and architecture, which are being actively used, will remain stable in our language. Because the introduction of new terms into our lexicon as an acquired layer is causing the word used before to become inactive and archaic along with the thing it meant. Examples of this are terms such as rabat, castle, maqbara, burj, mezana, sharafa, fanus, koshin, muqarnas.

The people are the main participants in the process of the popularization and assimilation of the terms of the acquired layer into our language. Language is a community asset. The members of the society make regular contacts with each other. During communication, the words in the language change over time, some words become historical and leave the communication process, while some become modern and become an active lexeme among members of society (this process is carried out in most cases at the expense of foreign words).

Linguistics has widely studied the issue of term creation and the interaction between the bases of artificial terms. In terminological studies, it is thought that the formation of terms is carried out mainly in 3 different ways. These are: affixal, compositional and semantic methods. The formation of a term in sources is almost no different from the formation of a word in the language. But in some places, the introduction of common words plays an important role in the

formation of terms. The method of calking also plays a significant role in the creation of terms. But in this process, Russian or foreign words introduced through the Russian language also become popular, move to the national language or become a component of the provision of a certain field. Any profession, be it architecture or any other type, contains certain words and phrases that are related to the scope of application and clearly express the field.

After a few years, a group of words becomes inactive, giving way to newly introduced words. But some terms are still used in their meaning. Because the semantic and stylistic meanings of the words are not exactly the same, this happens. For example, plaster, marble, paint, glass.

1. Most of the words used in the field of architecture and construction are translated words. In such lexemes, the stylistic and social status of the vocabulary of the language plays an important role. Today, among the terms in this field, there are many lexemes that came from the English language.

2. First of all, the reason for the appropriation of terms is that various countries widely use English as an international language in creating high-tech tools and popularizing them and putting them on the world market, naming their products. Therefore, most of the new terms entering our social life are in this language. Secondly, the brevity of words and phrases used in English makes it easier to master. Below we will consider some terms related to the field of architecture and construction that are used with the same name in both English and Uzbek:

3. **Arch** - a gate, door, window, etc., with a semicircular top.

4. **Balcony** - a porch, a square built on the second and higher floors of a multi-story building, attached to the interior rooms, and its front, back, or sides facing the outside, yard or street.

5. **Bracket** - a device used to install a shelf on the wall.

6. **Entasis** - is used in the work of the column, i.e., the decoration that thins the upper part of the column from the middle to the capitell with a special circular line.

7. **Facade** - house, front side of the building.

8. **Corridor** - a corridor serving for access to rooms inside the building and communication between rooms.

9. **Panel** - is a wooden, plastic or oil-painted decorative coating of a wall inside a building.

10. **Project** - project.

11. **Terrace** - light summer porch, porch.

12. **Reconstruction** - radical reconstruction of an existing thing (enterprise, city, building) in order to improve it, increase its practical value, improve it.

Acquisitions are one of the sources of regularity of development and enrichment of any language. The acquisition process is a complex phenomenon and is closely connected with linguistic and extralinguistic factors.

Currently, special attention is being paid to the provision of housing to the population in different regions of our country and the construction of multi-storey buildings that fully meet the requirements of the time. If we take the example of our capital alone, investments are made from abroad in the construction of hundreds of modernized residential buildings, and foreign architects and builders are involved in the construction work. This, in turn, creates the ground for foreign terms in this field to enter our language as neologisms. Below are examples of such lexemes:

1. "Hi-tech" style. In recent years, the term "high-tech" has been actively used in the field of architecture. In English, the word "hi-tech" means "high technology". This term is used in our language for modern home renovation based on high technologies.

2. Hall An area of a house or building leading to individual rooms. Forms a semantic synonymy with the lexeme hall. The lexeme hall is used in the language as a component of public buildings, and the lexeme "hall" is now more widely used for residential buildings than for public buildings.

3. Building. A structure built for living, working and other needs of people, a huge house, building. It forms a semantic synonymy with the building lexeme. The term "building" is used to refer to modern high-rise buildings, as well as to the name of a construction company. For example, "Murad buildings", "Brilliant building", "Simple building" and others.

4. House. A place built for people to live. Currently, it is used for high-rise residential buildings and their designation. For example, "Golden house", "Star house", "Dream house", etc.

It is known that sectoral terminology is enriched by taking words from common lexical units belonging to its layer based on the internal capabilities of the language, and the acceptance of the lexical unit as terminology is often carried out based on the phenomena of metaphor and metonymy. At this point, it should be said that the terms, in turn, serve for the emergence of certain linguistic units, in particular, lexemes, word combinations, collocations, and stable combinations in the common language. In the process of termination, the non-termination of the terminological unit, as well as the widespread reliance on metaphor and metonymy phenomena, is understood by transferring the metaphorical and metonymic meaning. We can actively encounter this in the process of social communication of communicants or in the discourse of an artistic work. For example: in the process of daily communication in the Uzbek language, we actively meet such stable combinations and collocations.

Today, the increasing popularity of electronic dictionaries in mobile form makes it necessary to form and electronicize the dictionary base of architectural and construction terms, and in this process to accept them as terms by analyzing the terms of the field that exist in social communication, and at the same time to transfer the terms that are out of date from the social language to the base of the dictionary of obsolete terms. or it requires taking alternative equivalents of the newly acquired terms from among archaic terms and national language units and preserving the semantic and stylistic linguistic features of the term.